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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FAST DISSOLVING
SUBLINGUAL FILM OF ATORVASTATIN CALCIUM****G. Gnanarajan*, Garima Thapliyal,**Department of Pharmaceutics, School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Shri Guru Ram Rai
University Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India - 248001**Article Received:** September 2020**Accepted:** October 2020**Published:** November 2020**Abstract:**

Atorvastatin calcium (ATC) is the most effective and best tolerated agent for treating Coronary heart disease. ATC is unstable and at risk to heat, light, and moisture when packed in the form of tablets, powders, granules, or within capsules. In acidic environment it degrades into corresponding lactone. This instability of ATC leading to poor solubility is the main cause for low bioavailability of the drug after oral administration as the absolute bioavailability of ATC is only 14%. Therefore, aim of the research is to improve the oral bioavailability by formulating it into a fast dissolving sublingual film. Formulations were prepared composed of HPMC E15, HPMC K15M and Pectin as a film forming agent; Crospovidone, Sodium starch glycolate, and Croscarmellose sodium as a superdisintegrating agent; Polyethylene glycol as a plasticizer; citric acid as a saliva stimulating agent; mannitol as a sweetening agent; methanol and water as a solvent. Different film formulations of Atorvastatin calcium were prepared by using HPMC E15, HPMC K15M, Pectin, Crospovidone. Different formulations were prepared by varying concentration of (polymers and disintegrating agent) ratio by solvent casting method. The compatibility study of drug and excipients was performed by IR study and no interaction was found. The prepared films were clear, transparent and smooth surface. The percentage moisture uptake and percentage moisture loss were found to be high for the patches formulated with HPMC E15 and HPMC K15M when compared to the film formulated with pectin. Folding endurance of HPMC E15 and HPMC K15M containing films were found to be higher than the other films which might be due to the nature of the polymers. The formulations F1-F3 showed a better in vitro disintegration time (13-14 seconds), when compared to the other formulations. Optimized batch F1 containing containing hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (500mg) and crospovidone(30mg) showed in vitro drug release (98.33%) within 6 minutes. The formulations F1 showed a better in- vitro permeation study profile (95.61 within 11minute), when compared to the other formulations.

Keywords: Atorvastatin calcium, Coronary heart disease, bioavailability, fast dissolving sublingual film, film forming agent, in vitro dissolution study.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The Fast Dissolving Drug Delivery Systems was an advancement that started to be in the early 1970's and conflicts over the deployment of the tablets, syrups, capsules which are the other oral drug delivery system [1]. Fast Dissolving Drug Delivery Systems serves as a major assistance over the conventional dosage forms since the drug gets swiftly disintegrated and dissolves in the saliva without the use of water [2]. However, per-oral administration of drugs gives rise to some problems such as hepatic first pass metabolism and degradation within the GI tract. These problems can be overcome by administration through the sublingual mucosa. The sublingual route can produce a quick onset of action within a short period of time due to

high permeability and vascularization of the sublingual mucosa. Fast dissolving film is prepared using hydrophilic polymers that quickly dissolve or disintegrate within few seconds[3]. It delivers direct admittance into the systemic circulation thereby evading the hepatic first pass effect and ease of administration. This delivery system comprises of a thin film, is simply placed underneath the tongue, promptly wet by saliva; the film quickly dissolves. Then it rapidly disintegrates and dissolves to release the medication for systemic absorption. This fast dissolving action is mainly due to the huge surface area of the film, which wets rapidly when exposed to the moist sublingual environment. (Figure No.1)

Fig .1. Structure of Oral Mucosa

Hyperlipidemia, or high cholesterol, refers to elevated levels of fats in the blood. Most people do not usually experience any symptoms, but having hyperlipidemia increases the risk of developing heart disease and increases the risk of stroke and death. Hyperlipidemia means there is too much cholesterol in the blood. Cholesterol is a waxy fat molecule that the liver produces. It is essential for healthy cell membranes, brain functioning, hormone production, and vitamin storage. There are two types of proteins, or

lipoproteins, that transport cholesterol to the cells: Low-density lipoproteins (LDL), or bad cholesterol, and high-density lipoproteins (HDL), or good cholesterol. LDL has damaging effects on health. HDL, however, counteracts the effects of LDL. HDL is good for health as it carries excess cholesterol back to the liver for excretion. The liver then eliminates cholesterol through bile. LDL that remains in the bloodstream damages health, because it allows excess cholesterol to build up in the blood.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. MATERIALS:

Atorvastatin calcium was the gift sample obtained from Baxil Pharma Pvt. Ltd. Shyampur Haridwar. HPMC E15, HPMC K15M and Pectin were generously gifted by Central Drug House (P) Ltd, New Delhi. Crospovidone, Sodium starch glycolate, and Crosscarmellose sodium gifted by Central Drug House (P) Ltd, New Delhi. Mannitol, citric acid and PEG 400 were generously gifted by Central Drug House (P) Ltd, New Delhi. Methanol was gifted by Central Drug House (P) Ltd, New Delhi. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

2.2. METHOD:

2.2.1. UV spectroscopy determination of absorbance maxima[75,104]

To determination of absorbance maxima Atorvastatin calcium, a standard solution of drug is prepared by dissolving 100mg drug in 100ml to obtain a solution 1000 μ g/ml. From this solution, 1ml of solution was pipette out in 10ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to 10ml with the help of 9ml of solvent to prepare a stock solution of 100 μ g/ml. from the stock solution, dilution of 10 μ g/ml was prepared and analyzed by UV between 200-400nm to obtain maximum wavelength of drug.

2.2.2. Preparation of standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in different solvents[4,5]

Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium is prepared in water, phosphate buffer pH6.8, phosphate buffer pH7.4 and Methanol.

1. Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in water:

a. Standard solution

Standard solution of Atorvastatin calcium was prepared by dissolving 100mg of drug in water in volumetric flask and volume was make up to 100ml with the help of water. The concentration was found to be 1000 μ g/ml.

b. Stock solution:

From the standard stock solution was prepared by pipette out 10ml of standard solution into 100ml of volumetric flask and volume was made up to 100ml with the help of water, to make the solution having 100 μ g/ml concentration.

c. Preparation of working standard solution [6]

From the stock solution (100 μ g/ml) aliquots of 0.5ml, 1ml, 1.5ml, 2ml, 2.5ml, 3ml were pipette out and placed into placed into 10ml of volumetric flasks.

Then the volume was made up to the calibrated mark with the help of water. This solution provides 5 μ g/ml, 10 μ g/ml, 15 μ g/ml, 20 μ g/ml, 25 μ g/ml concentration of Atorvastatin calcium.

Now from the standard solution (1000 μ g/ml) aliquots of 0.5ml, 1ml, 1.5ml, 2ml, 2.5ml, 3ml

Was pipette out and placed into 10ml of volumetric flasks. Then the volume was made up to the calibrated mark with the help of water. This solution provides 5 μ g/ml, 10 μ g/ml, 15 μ g/ml, 20 μ g/ml, 25 μ g/ml concentration of Atorvastatin calcium. The absorbance of prepared solutions of Atorvastatin calcium was measured at 246nm respectively using UV- Visible Spectrophotometer against an appropriate blank.

2.2.3. Compatibility studies of drug and selected polymer by using FT-IR [7,8]

For the determination of compatibility of Atorvastatin calcium with respected polymer (HPMC E15, HPMC K15M and Pectin). Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Spectrum TwoTM) was used. For the determination of IR spectra for compatibility study of drug and polymer KBr disc method was used. In KBr disc method, drug sample and respected polymer (1:1) was taken and finely grounded with the help mortar and pestle made up of agate. Then the drug sample was mixed with 100mg of dry potassium bromide powder to obtain a uniform mixture. The mixture is then converted into a transparent disc or pellets in an evacuable die by applying sufficient high pressure by using the device hydraulic press. For the base line correction dried potassium bromide was used. To, obtain the spectrum the pellet made up of mixture (drug, polymer and potassium bromide) was scanned between 2000-1 to 4000-1.

2.3. Preparation of fast dissolving thin strips of Atorvastatin calcium[9,10,11]

Fast dissolving sublingual film was prepared by using solvent casting method

Fast dissolving films are ideally formulated using the solvent casting method, whereby the water-soluble ingredients are dissolved to form a clear viscous solution and the drug along with different excipients is dissolved in a suitable solvent then both the solutions are mixed and stirred and lastly casted into the Petri plate and dried. (Table No.2)

Table No.2. Composition of fast dissolving sublingual film of Atorvastatin calcium

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Atorvastatin calcium	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
HPMC E15	500	500	500	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMC K15M	-	-	-	500	500	500	-	-	-
Pectin	-	-	-	-	-	-	500	500	500
Crospovidone	30	-	-	30	-	-	30	-	-
Sodium starch glycolate	-	30	-	-	30	-	-	30	-
Crosscarmellose sodium	-	-	30	-	-	30	-	-	30
Polyethylene glycol 400	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Citric acid	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Mannitol	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Methanol	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Water	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

Polymer and other water soluble ingredients were dissolved in water with stirring at 1000rpm

Polymer solution /suspension + miscibility of drug and polymer + temperature during mixing

API and other excipients were dissolved in 5ml of methanol

Air entrapment + viscosity of the solution/ suspension

Now both the solutions were mixed by thoroughly stirring at 1000rpm for 1 hour

The solution was kept overnight to remove air bubbles to form clear solution

5ml of solution was taken and poured into the petriplate and kept at room temperature

Drying temperature + drying time+ moisture control

After 24 hours, film was formed and cut into the pieces of desired size

Calculation of amount of drug incorporate:

Diameter of petridish = 9.2cm

Radius of petridish = 4.6cm

Area of petridish = $\pi r^2 = 3.14 \times 4.6 \times 4.6 = 66.44\text{cm}^2$

4cm² contain 20 mg of Drug

A no. of 4cm² films obtained from the main film = $66.44/4 = 16.61$

Approximately 16 films obtained with area of 4cm²

The amount of drug should be incorporated in the area considered is calculated as follows:

16 films X 20mg = **320mg**

2.4. Evaluation parameters of formulated Fast Dissolving Sublingual Film:**2.4.1. Organoleptic Evaluation** [12,13]

- a) **Appearance:** - Appearance of the formulated strips were done by visual inspection and then strips were categorized as best, good, average and bad.
- b) **Transparency:** - Transparency evaluation of formulated strips were done by visual inspection and then strips were categorized as transparent, semi-transparent and opaque.
- c) **Surface texture:** - Surface texture of formulated strips were done by visual method and visual inspection and then strips were categorized from smooth to rough surface which indicated by ++ mathematical sign.
(Figure No.11)

2.4.2. Weight variation [14,15]

For calculation of weight variation 3 films (2cm²) from each formulation were taken and weighed individually by using digital balance. The weight of each film was noted down. The average weight and standard deviation was calculated.

2.4.3. Thickness [16,17]

The thickness of the patch was measured using digital Vernier Caliper at different spots of the film. The thickness was measured at three different spots of the patch and average was taken and SD was calculated.

2.4.4. Folding endurance[16,18,19]

Folding endurance was determined by repeated folding of the film at the same place till the strip breaks. The number of times the film is folded without breaking was computed as the folding endurance value.

2.4.5. Surface pH[18,20]

The film to be tested was placed in a petri dish and was moistened with 0.5ml of distilled water and kept for 30sec. The pH was noted after bringing the electrode of the pH meter in contact with the surface of the formulation and allowing equilibration for 1min. The

average of three determinations for each formulation was done.

2.4.6. Percent Moisture uptake[11,21]

This test is usually done to determine the physical stability of the strips in high humid conditions. For the determination of %moisture loss 3 films 2cm² was taken and weighed individually by using digital balance. Now, the film were placed to desiccator for the period of 72 hours. After 72 hours the strips were removed and exposed to the saturated solution of aluminium chloride and reweighed. The average percent moisture uptake of film was calculated by using formula:-

$$\% \text{Moisture Uptake} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial Weight}}{\text{Final weight}} \times 100$$

2.4.7. Percent Moisture loss[22,23]

This test is usually done to determine the physical stability and integrity of the formulated strips at the dry conditions. For the determination of % moisture loss 3 films of 2cm² was taken and weighed individually by using digital balance. Now, the film were placed in desiccator containing fused anhydrous calcium chloride (inside the desiccator) for the period of 72 hours. After 72 hours the strips were removed and reweighed. The average percent moisture loss of film was calculated by using formula-

$$\% \text{Moisture Loss} = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial Weight}}{\text{Final weight}} \times 100$$

2.4.8. Uniformity of drug content [24,25,26]

The film of 2cm² was taken and dissolved in 25ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8. Then the solution was sonicated for 15 minutes with the help of sonicator for complete solubilisation of film. Then the solution was filtered through whatman filter paper. If necessary, dilution was done and the solution was analyzed by using UV- Visible spectrophotometer at 246nm for the determination of absorbance.

This experiment is repeated by using 3 films from each formulation and absorbance was noted down to obtain

the average value and further calculation was done to determination the percent drug content.

2.4.9. Disintegration Test [28,29]

The disintegration test was done by using petridish method. In this method 2-3ml of distilled water was taken in the petridish and the film of 2cm² was placed on the petridish. The time required by the film to dissolve was noted down. This experiment is done by using three strips from each formulation. After that average was calculated and standard deviation was calculated.

2.4.10. In vitro dissolution studies [24,27]

The in vitro dissolution study can be carried out in 500 ml pH 6.8 phosphate buffer using (USP) XIV paddle apparatus II at 37 \pm 0.5 $^{\circ}$ C and at 50r/min. Each square cut film sample is immersed into the dissolution media and appropriate aliquots were withdrawn at definite intervals for 30 min. The drug concentration is measured by a UV spectro-photometer.

2.4.11. In- vitro pharmacokinetic study [15,30]

For the release kinetic study the data obtained from the in-vitro dissolution studies was incorporated to zero order, first order, Higuchi matrix and Korsmeyer Peppas model. The aim behind the kinetic study was to determine the release mechanism of drug from the dosage form. This was done by comparing the r² value of each formulation which determine the best fit model and by observing the n value of all the formulation which gives the idea of mechanism of drug release from the prepared formulation.

- **Zero order:** The graph was plotted between % cumulative release v/s time.
- **First order:** The graph was plotted between Log% ARA v/s time.
- **Higuchi matrix:** The graph was plotted between % cumulative release v/s \sqrt{t} .
- **Korsmeyer- Peppas model:** The graph was plotted between Log% cumulative release v/s Log t.

- **Hixson-crowell model:** The graph was plotted between Cubic root of % ARA and time.

2.4.12. In- vitro permeation studies [5,25]

In- vitro permeation studies was carried out by using Franz diffusion cell. For this, egg shell membrane was used to resemble the buccal mucosa and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 was used as a medium. The membrane was placed between the donor and the receptor compartment. The receptor compartment was filled with the suitable volume of the medium and the temperature was maintained at 37 $^{\circ}$ C and then it was placed over the magnetic stirrer for maintain the hydrodynamics. Then the film of 2cm² (20mg drug) was placed on the donor compartment. Then from the receptor compartment aliquots (2ml) of sample was taken at 1 minute time interval and same volume was maintained by replacing with freshly prepared same dissolution medium. The absorbance of the samples was measured at 246nm respectively by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer against an appropriate blank.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1. UV spectroscopy determination of absorbance maxima [6,31]

As per the observed data the absorption maxima of test was found to be 246nm in phosphate buffer pH 6.8, which comply with standard value. shown in Figure No.2.

3.2. Preparation of standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in different solvents

Discussion:- Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium was prepared in different solvents. Graph between absorbance and corresponding concentration were plotted. The obtained r² value were 0.9984, 0.9944, 0.998 and 0.9996 in corresponding solvent phosphate buffer pH 6.8, phosphate buffer pH 7.4, water and methanol. The r² value of sample suggest linearity in equation. Thus this equation can be used for further calculation purpose. (Table No.1) (Figure No.3,4,5 and 6)

Table No.1. Standard curve data of Atorvastatin calcium in different solvents

Sr. No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance(nm)			
		Phosphate buffer pH 6.8	Phosphate buffer pH 7.4	Water	Methanol
1	5	0.2914	0.1898	0.1992	0.3041
2	10	0.4512	0.3917	0.3416	0.4627
3	15	0.5995	0.5967	0.5392	0.6084
4	20	0.7892	0.7471	0.7192	0.7494
5	25	0.9313	0.9021	0.8913	0.9079

Fig .2. Absorption maxima of Atorvastatin calcium

Fig .3. Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

Fig .4. Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in phosphate buffer pH 7.4

Fig .5. Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in water

Fig .6. Standard curve of Atorvastatin calcium in methanol

3.3. Compatibility studies of drug and polymer by using FT-IR[7,8]

Discussion: IR spectra of Atorvastatin calcium (Figured No.7) was compared with IR spectra of pure drug + HPMC K 15M (Figured No.8), pure drug + HPMC E15 (Figured No.9) pure drug + pectin (Figured No.10). By comparing the obtained spectra between pure drug. Drug + HPMC K 15M, pure drug + HPMC E15 and pure drug + pectin there is no significant difference observed. So it revealed no chemical interaction.

Fig .7. FT-IR spectra of Atorvastatin calcium

Fig .8. FT-IR spectra of Atorvastatin calcium + HPMC K15M

Fig .9. FTIR spectra of Atorvastatin calcium + HPMC E15

Fig .10. FTIR spectra of Atorvastatin calcium + Pectin

3.4. Determination of Weight uniformity[14,15]

Discussion: The weight of all prepared formulation was observed in between 62.91 ± 0.28 to 72.12 ± 0.22 (Table No.3 and Figure No.12). As per the obtained results all films are relatively similar in weight which shows uniform distribution of API and excipient on the surface of the films.

3.5. Determination of Thickness[16,17]

The thickness of all prepared formulation was found in between 0.146 ± 0.010 to 0.170 ± 0.005 (Table No.3 and Figure No.13). As per the obtained result it was observed that there is no remarkable change in the thickness of the films so it can be concluded that there is uniform distribution of API and excipient throughout the surface of the films.

Table No.3. Weight uniformity result of prepared formulation

Sr. No.	Formulation code	Weight (mg) Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)	Thickness(m m) Mean \pm 4S.D. (n=3)	Folding endurance Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)	Surface pH Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)	Percentage moisture uptake Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)	Percentage moisture loss Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)
1	F1	65.90 \pm 0.31	0.146 \pm 0.010	275 \pm 1.452	6.67 \pm 0.156	15.74 \pm 0.53	10.23 \pm 0.42
2	F2	62.91 \pm 0.28	0.140 \pm 0.005	288 \pm 1.000	6.00 \pm 0.112	15.44 \pm 0.66	9.53 \pm 0.74
3	F3	66.84 \pm 0.38	0.144 \pm 0.015	285 \pm 2.340	6.65 \pm 0.115	13.88 \pm 0.96	8.33 \pm 0.27
4	F4	72.12 \pm 0.22	0.150 \pm 0.010	272 \pm 1.730	6.23 \pm 0.125	11.62 \pm 0.35	8.96 \pm 0.40
5	F5	63.92 \pm 0.41	0.165 \pm 0.005	289 \pm 2.640	6.06 \pm 0.153	12.36 \pm 0.28	10.85 \pm 0.43
6	F6	65.96 \pm 0.31	0.160 \pm 0.005	266 \pm 3.310	6.76 \pm 0.173	12.65 \pm 0.56	7.22 \pm 0.36
7	F7	68.21 \pm 0.23	0.156 \pm 0.010	259 \pm 1.365	6.80 \pm 0.100	10.56 \pm 0.76	6.85 \pm 0.87
8	F8	70.03 \pm 0.08	0.170 \pm 0.005	277 \pm 2.000	6.63 \pm 0.175	9.56 \pm 0.44	9.63 \pm 0.35
9	F9	67.56 \pm 0.12	0.166 \pm 0.010	271 \pm 2.340	6.30 \pm 0.111	8.71 \pm 0.25	6.56 \pm 0.92

Formulation 1

Formulation 2

Formulation 3

Formulation 4

Formulation 5

Formulation 6

Formulation 7

Formulation 8

Formulation 9

Figure No.11. Prepared fast dissolving sublingual films from F1-F9

Fig .12. Bar diagram showing weight uniformity of prepared formulation from F1-F9

Fig .13. Bar diagram showing thickness of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.6. Determination of folding endurance[16,18,19]

The value of folding endurance of all prepared formulations was found in between 259 ± 1.365 to 289 ± 2.640 (Table No.3 and Figure No.14). As per the obtained result it was observed all films are relatively similar in folding endurance. The folding endurance value generally determines the ability of the films to withstand rupture.

Fig .14. Bar diagram showing Folding endurance of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.7. Determination of Surface pH[18,20]

The value of pH of all prepared formulations was observed in between 6.00 ± 0.112 to 6.80 ± 0.100 (Table No.3 and Figure No.15). As per the obtained value was observed that the pH of all films are near to neutral (there is no remarkable difference in pH of the film and pH of saliva) which indicate that there will be not any kind of irritation or side effects to the mucosal lining of the oral cavity after administration of the formulated films.

Fig .15. Bar diagram showing Surface pH of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.8. Determination of Percentage Moisture uptake[11,21]

The value of percent moisture uptake of all prepared formulation observed in between 8.71 ± 0.25 to 15.74 ± 0.53 (Table No.3 and Figure No.16). The percentage moisture uptake value generally determines the physical stability of the formulated films when exposed to high humid conditions.

Fig .16. Bar diagram showing Percentage moisture uptake of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.9. Determination of percentage moisture loss[22,23]

The value of percent moisture loss of all prepared formulation ranges was found in between 6.56 ± 0.92 to 10.23 ± 0.42 (Table No.3 and Figure No.17). The percentage moisture loss value generally determines the physical stability and integrity of the formulated films when exposed to dry conditions.

Fig .17. Bar diagram showing Percentage moisture loss of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.10. Determination of drug content[24,25,26]

The content uniformity test was performed to ensure uniform distribution of the drug. The content uniformity was performed for all the formulations. The results indicated that in all the formulations that there was good uniformity in drug content which ranged between 94.66 ± 0.22 to 98.32 ± 0.63 (Table No.4 and Figure No.18)

Fig .18. Bar diagram showing Drug content of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.11. In- Vitro disintegration time[28,29]

Discussion: The value of in- vitro disintegration study of formulated films ranges from 12 ± 0.45 to 16 ± 0.56 (Table No.4 and Figure No.19). As per the obtained value it was observed that there no significant difference in disintegration time of all formulation but the formulation F1 which contain HPMC E5 as polymer and crospovidone as superdisintegrants shows less disintegration time as compared to other formulation.

Table No.4. Drug content result of prepared formulations

Sr. No.	Formulation code	Percentage Drug content Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)	In- Vitro disintegration time Mean \pm S.D. (n=3)
1	F1	95.86 \pm 1.26	13 \pm 0.11
2	F2	98.32 \pm 0.63	13 \pm 0.74
3	F3	94.66 \pm 0.22	14 \pm 0.62
4	F4	97.88 \pm 0.41	16 \pm 0.14
5	F5	98.46 \pm 0.17	14 \pm 0.54
6	F6	97.14 \pm 0.79	15 \pm 0.66
7	F7	96.08 \pm 0.88	16 \pm 0.56
8	F8	95.99 \pm 0.14	14 \pm 0.45
9	F9	96.36 \pm 0.75	16 \pm 0.26

Fig .19. Bar diagram showing In-Vitro disintegration time of prepared formulation from F1-F9

3.12. In- Vitro dissolution studies[24,27]

The cumulative percent drug release from all prepared formulation was ranging between 79.63% to 98.33% (Table No.5 and Figure No.20) during study period. From the in- vitro dissolution studies it was observed that the formulation F1 which contain HPMC E5 as polymer and croscopovidone as superdisintegrant shows maximum drug release (98.33%) within 6 minutes. The rate of drug release was faster because the solubility of HPMC E5 was high and the croscopovidone which was used as superdisintegrant act by combination of three mechanism wicking, swelling, and deformation which ultimately leads to the higher wettability and penetration of water in the film matrices which increased the rate of dissolution of drug.

Table No.5. Cumulative % drug release data of prepared formulation

Sr. No.	Time (min)	% Cumulative Release								
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	23.7	19.58	16.2	17.69	15.06	19.30	11.81	18.6	12.80
3	2	51.95	46.9	40.88	39.22	39.9	38.11	32.47	35.78	38.20
4	3	69.47	61.25	60.23	60.1	50.6	51.25	49.83	48.21	51.30
5	4	82.9	78.55	77.3	76.19	69.36	65.14	57.92	62.47	60.48
6	5	91.6	86.88	84.9	83.9	79.75	77.51	68.80	74.23	73.02
7	6	98.33	97.56	94.8	92.61	88.55	85.27	79.63	83.44	81.33

Fig .20. In- vitro drug release data of prepared formulation F1-F9

3.13. In- vitro pharmacokinetic studies[15,30]

From the obtained experimental data it was clearly observed that by comparing the r^2 value hixson- crowell is most dominant in F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F9 formulation except F8 (Table No.6 and Figure No.21,22,23,24 and 25) which means that the drug release on the time. By observing the value of release exponent (n) from korsmeyer – peppas model it was concluded that the non-fickian or anomalous diffusion was dominant in which the release of the drug the film matrices was depend on polymeric chains relaxation when came in contact with the solvent.

Table No.6. Result of correlation coefficients data of prepared formulation F1- F9

Sr. No.	Formulation code	Zero order (r^2)	First order (r^2)	Higuchi matrix (r^2)	Hixson Crowell (r^2)	Korsmeyer-peppas		Best fit model	Mechanism of release
						(r^2)	n		
1	F1	0.9443	0.9200	0.9301	0.9924	0.9638	0.7885	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
2	F2	0.9691	0.8910	0.9263	0.9770	0.9711	0.8806	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
3	F3	0.9718	0.9459	0.9283	0.9892	0.9708	0.9838	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
4	F4	0.9709	0.9687	0.9264	0.9941	0.9788	0.9354	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
5	F5	0.9806	0.9696	0.9245	0.9919	0.9723	0.9741	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
6	F6	0.9833	0.9807	0.9191	0.9971	0.9943	0.8317	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian
7	F7	0.9813	0.9819	0.9273	0.9933	0.9681	1.0414	Hixson-Crowell	Supercase II Transport
8	F8	0.9886	0.9779	0.9169	0.9958	0.9973	0.8392	Korsmeyer- Peppas	Non-fickian
9	F9	0.9725	0.9864	0.9294	0.9944	0.9520	0.9977	Hixson-Crowell	Non-fickian

Fig .21. Zero order kinetic profile of formulation F1 to F9

Fig .22. First order kinetic profile of formulation F1 to F9

Fig .23. Higuchi kinetic profile of formulation F1 to F9

Fig .24. Korsmeyer- peppas kinetic profile of formulation F1 to F9

Fig .25. Hixson crowell kinetic profile of formulation F1 to F9

Fig .26. In- vitro permeation of formulations F1 to F9

3.14. *In- vitro* permeation study[5,25]

Discussion: The % permeation of all the prepared formulations was ranging between 82.23 to 95.61 (Table No.7 and Figure No.26) during study period. The formulation F1 which contain HPMC E15 as film forming polymer and crospovidone as superdisintegrant shows maximum drug permeation (95.61%) within minimum time (11minutes) period when compared to other formulations which indicates excellent drug permeation, which is the basic requirement in case of fast dissolving formulation to minimize the first pass metabolism of drug to enhance the bioavailability and for faster onset of action.

Table No.7. In- vitro permeation study data of prepared formulation

Sr. No.	Time (min)	% Drug permeate								
		F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	1	15.96	12.55	14.78	16.33	13.99	12.01	10.66	11.05	10.01
3	2	31.33	23.48	27.12	21.89	28.74	23.68	19.42	20.48	17.56
4	3	38.85	33.16	36.99	28.23	34.25	30.46	26.25	26.91	25.21
5	4	50.12	41.28	48.47	34.31	39.88	36.78	30.11	33.86	29.43
6	5	58.79	49.73	56.99	41.92	47.48	47.44	34.52	38.47	31.86
7	6	65.24	59.31	64.29	55.19	55.17	56.29	38.99	43.78	36.49
8	7	72.16	65.24	70.69	61.07	60.46	64.11	43.73	49.55	40.22
9	8	77.51	72.68	73.88	66.99	64.22	70.77	50.57	54.42	46.52
10	9	84.45	78.94	80.19	72.48	69.53	76.41	57.29	60.66	51.89
11	10	89.99	84.62	85.45	77.64	75.36	80.89	65.78	66.54	57.33
12	11	95.61	89.56	88.31	80.32	79.85	84.55	70.66	73.46	68.75
13	12	-	93.22	92.36	85.15	88.12	89.53	74.32	78.85	72.99
14	13	-	-	-	88.96	90.99	-	79.16	82.43	77.56
15	14	-	-	-	91.58	-	-	83.73	85.69	82.23

4. CONCLUSION:

The present work was proposed to prepare fast dissolving sublingual film with Atorvastatin calcium to achieve better bioavailability with low dose of the drug at the site, decreased the risk of adverse side effects based on *in-vitro* released study. Atorvastatin calcium sublingual film were prepared by solvent casting method for all the formulations F1 to F9.

From this investigation, it was concluded that formulation F1 with HPMC E15 as film forming agent and crospovidone as a superdisintegrating agent may be the best formulation having good *in vitro* release profile and bioavailability.

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